

Burr removal from high-aspect-ratio micro-pillars using ultrasonic-assisted abrasive micro-deburring

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Abstract

The demand for high-aspect-ratio microstructures is ever increasing in the fields of MEMS, biomedicine, aerospace, telecommunication, and heat transfer. Mechanical micromachining processes have a distinct advantage over lithography-based processes for machining complex three-dimensional microstructures on a variety of materials with high accuracy and surface finish. But the tool-based micromachining operations face inherent issues in the form of excessive burr formation, which needs to be addressed by post-machining burr removal operations. In this study, an ultrasonic-assisted abrasive micro-deburring process employing a probe sonotrode and abrasive particles has been investigated for deburring high-aspect-ratio micro-pillars machined on aluminium 6061 and copper. Deburring of micromilled pillars of aspect ratio 5:1 has been achieved while maintaining pillar integrity. The mechanism of deburring has been observed to be mainly by the impact of the abrasive particles with a minor role played by liquid cavitation. Burr reduction as high as 88.75% for Al 6061 and 90.1% for copper has been achieved in a short processing time of 10 s. This is a significantly faster process than other ultrasonic cavitation-based deburring processes described in literature (deburring time ranging from 60 min to a few hours). With proper control of the process parameters like stand-off distance and power, burr removal has been achieved while maintaining the integrity of the micro-pillars. Pure water cavitation has also been studied for comparison, which has resulted in a burr removal by 51.5% and 53.1% for Al 6061 and copper, respectively. Upon proper selection of the process parameters, this process can be a viable alternative to existing deburring methods in terms of minimal processing time and structure damage.

Keywords: micro-deburring, micromilling, ultrasonic, abrasive, micro-pillar, high-aspect-ratio

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1 Introduction

High-aspect-ratio microstructures refer to microfeatures with an aspect ratio greater than 2 and width usually less than 4 mm [1]. The demand for high-aspect-ratio microstructures has been increasing in various applications like microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) [2], heat transfer [3], aerospace [4], and biomedicine [5]. Fabrication of these microstructures has been achieved using processes like LIGA [6], injection moulding [7], etching and electroplating [8], and tool-based machining [9]. The machining of high-aspect-ratio microstructures has remained a significant challenge owing to the poor machinability of materials at the micro-scale that results in inferior surface quality and burr formation.

Mechanical micromachining has some specific advantages over other micromachining processes like the ability to machine complex three-dimensional (3D) geometric features on a variety of materials like metals, polymers, ceramics, and composites with high accuracy and surface quality that is difficult to achieve by other processes [10]. This makes them particularly useful in the generation of microstructures with high-aspect-ratios. Llanos et al. [9] have conducted experimental studies to explore the process capabilities for micromilling thin walls on aluminium alloy (Al 6061 – T4) and brass. They have reported that by optimising tool path strategy and machining parameters like speed, feed, and axial depth of cut, thin walls can be machined with better quality and minimum thickness deviation. Li et al. [11] have reported the successful machining of thin ribs on Böhler M261 steel with an aspect ratio as high as 54 (width $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$, height $\sim 800 \mu\text{m}$) while achieving an acceptable rib shape and surface quality.

Tool-based micromachining processes such as micromilling are usually accompanied by the formation of burrs whose dimension is often comparable to the dimension of the component. This is widely attributed to the larger cutting edge radius to uncut chip thickness ratio which causes more rubbing and ploughing [12]. Kiswanto et al. [13] have investigated the effect of cutting parameters and machining time on the surface roughness and burr formation during micromilling of aluminium 1100 alloy. They have observed that upmilling causes smaller burrs than downmilling and reported that burr formation can be minimised by selecting appropriate machining parameters like feed and cutting velocity. Saptaji and Subbiah [14] have reported the use of tapered micromilling tools to generate burr-free microfeatures on aluminium 6061. In another study, Vazquez et al. [15] have evaluated different cooling and lubricating strategies during micromilling Ti-6Al-4V and reported that minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) has resulted in minimal burr formation.

Past research has focused on burr minimisation, but burrs could not be completely removed by machining process alone, prompting a need for post-machining burr removal strategies. Kissling et al. [16] have attempted deburring of high-aspect-ratio

nickel RF MEMS using electropolishing technique. They have reported a burr removal rate between 1.0 and 1.8 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ but have observed edge-rounding on the structures. Jeong et al. [17] have successfully attempted deburring of micro-features on conductive materials using micro-EDM without causing any damage to the features. Kim et al. [18] have evaluated deburring of drilled holes in CFRP composites using large pulsed electron beam (LPEB) irradiations and have reported a burr removal by 97% and hole accuracy improvement by 93%. Egashira et al. [19] have investigated deburring of micro-holes in brass using specially fabricated micro-tools. By employing a helical tool feeding and ultrasonically oscillating the workpieces simultaneously, they could achieve successful deburring and edge finishing of holes as small as 0.2 mm. The use of ultrasonic cavitations for burr removal was first reported by Yeo et al. [20]. They have qualitatively demonstrated deburring of metallic and non-metallic burrs using ultrasonic cavitation energy in a bath sonicator. Horsch et al. [21] have reported the use of micro-peening and ultrasonic wet peening for deburring micro-mould inserts and have reported on the effectiveness of ultrasonic wet peening for deburring micromachined structures. However, a large processing time of up to 7 h was reported. Choi et al. [22] have evaluated the ultrasonic abrasive deburring of drilling burrs on aluminium using a probe sonotrode. They have reported better surface integrity and burr removal with the addition of abrasive as compared to pure cavitation. In another study, Kumar et al. [23] have investigated the ultrasonic-assisted abrasive micro-deburring of micro-channels on aluminium 6061, copper, Ti-6Al-4V, and bearing steel employing a probe sonotrode and alumina abrasive particles. They have reported a burr removal of up to 92% in a short processing time of 10 s without causing any deterioration to the dimensional tolerances. They have also reported an improvement in surface finish by 26%. The study, however, has not been tested for high-aspect-ratio microstructures.

In this study, an attempt is made to investigate the ultrasonic-assisted abrasive micro-deburring of high-aspect-ratio micro-pillars machined on aluminium 6061 and oxygen-free high-conductivity copper (OFHC) using a sonotrode. The influence of process parameters, namely stand-off distance and sonication power on the response parameters, namely pillar integrity and damage, deburring efficiency, and processing time will be systematically studied and conclusions will be drawn based on the observations.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Generation of micro-pillars

Aluminium 6061 and oxygen-free high-conductivity copper (OFHC) were used as work materials in the present study. The nominal mechanical properties of the work materials are shown in table 1. Workpieces of dimensions 20 mm \times 20 mm \times 6 mm

were procured and face-milled and polished on the 20 mm × 20 mm faces to achieve a parallelism of 0.0075 μm and a surface roughness of 44 nm. Micro-pillars of dimensions 100 μm × 100 μm × 500 μm (aspect ratio – 5:1) were machined on the prepared workpieces using two-flute TiAlN coated tungsten carbide micro-end milling cutter 500 μm in diameter (Axis Microtools, India) at a cutting velocity of 10 m min⁻¹ (spindle speed – 6400 rpm), feed of 1 μm per flute, and depth of cut of 25 μm. Machining of micro-pillars was undertaken on a high-precision CNC micromachining centre (Kern Evo). The machining centre has a resolution of 0.1 μm and a positional accuracy of ±0.5 μm. Dry cutting environment was used for machining the micro-pillars. Figure 1 shows a representational view of the micro-pillars with the top and the bottom burrs shown in the inset. The combination of low process parameters (feed and cutting velocity) and dry machining environment was intentionally used to generate large machining burrs so that the efficacy of the deburring process can be assessed.

Table 1. Nominal physical and mechanical properties of Al 6061 and copper [24–26]

Property	Al 6061	Copper
Density (kg m ⁻³)	2700	8940
Young's modulus (GPa)	68.9	117
Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	310	290
Poisson's ratio	0.33	0.30
Yield strength (MPa)	276	180–220
Shear strength (MPa)	207	180
Fracture toughness (MPa m ^{-1/2})	29	46
Hardness, Brinell	95	40
Charpy impact energy (J)	10–18	8–12

Figure 1. Representational view of machined micro-pillars with a close-up view showing top and bottom burrs

2.2 Deburring of micro-pillars

Deburring experiments were conducted on the machined micro-pillars using an ultrasonic-assisted abrasive micro-deburring process. Figure 2 shows the main components of the deburring setup. The setup consists of an ultrasonic probe sonotrode (PCI Analytics, India) which is made up of an ultrasonic transducer and a titanium horn (tip diameter: 13 mm), a height-adjustable platform, a temperature sensor, and a controller. The entire setup was enclosed in a sound-proof enclosure. The system is capable of generating ultrasonic vibrations at a frequency of 20 kHz and a maximum amplitude of 35 μm at a maximum power of 750 W, which can be varied from 0 to 100% using the controller.

Figure 2. Ultrasonic-abrasive assisted micro-deburring setup showing the main components (figure reproduced with permission from Kumar et al. [23]; copyright 2021 Elsevier)

Deburring fluid was prepared by adding alumina abrasive particles (size 2 μm – 5 μm) to deionised (DI) water at 3% w/w concentration and mixing in a magnetic stirrer at 1000 rpm for 24 h at a temperature of 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to obtain a uniform dispersion. 2% w/w sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) was added to keep the dispersion stable. Figure 3 shows the SEM image of the alumina particles used in the study. The particles selected were disc-shaped to facilitate deburring by particle-impact rather than micro cutting action, thereby minimising damage to the micro-pillars [23, 27]. Stable dispersions could not be prepared using larger particle size or higher abrasive concentration. Hence, abrasive particles of size 2 μm – 5 μm were used in the present study at a concentration of 3% w/w. The details of the deburring parameters used in the study are given in table 2. The workpiece was affixed to the bottom of a beaker using adhesive tape and mounted on the height-adjustable platform. The beaker was then filled with the

deburring fluid such that the workpiece, sonotrode horn, and the temperature sensor were immersed in the fluid. The height of the platform was adjusted to achieve the required stand-off distance between the workpiece surface and the sonotrode horn. Deburring experiments were conducted on the machined micro-pillars on both Al 6061 and copper workpieces at various stand-off distance and power values, as given in table 3. One experiment was conducted on each work material using pure water without abrasive particles to compare the effect of pure water cavitation with abrasive deburring. The temperature was maintained at 25 °C throughout the experiments.

Figure 3. SEM image of the abrasive alumina particles

Table 2. Details of the deburring parameters and setup specifications

Parameter	Value
Maximum power of the sonotrode	750 W
Frequency of the ultrasonic vibrations	20 kHz
Maximum amplitude	35 μm (at 750 W)
Composition of deburring fluid	3% w/w Al ₂ O ₃ abrasive particles in DI water
Mean size of the abrasives	2 μm – 5 μm
Surfactant used	2% w/w sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS)
Work material	Al 6061, OFHC
Dimensions of the micro-pillars	100 μm × 100 μm × 500 μm
Power settings	20%, 60%, 100% (at an SOD of 5 mm)
Stand-off distance (SOD)	2 mm, 5 mm, 8 mm (at a power of 100%)
Deburring time	30 s in steps of 10 s

After deburring, the workpieces were cleaned in acetone to remove debris and dried. Micrographs of the micro-pillars were captured using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Zeiss Evo 18) and the captured micrographs were analysed using image analysis software (Zeiss AxioVision, version 4.9.1). SEM images were captured and analysed after every ten seconds of deburring to study the deburring extent and pillar damage. The area of the top burrs on the micro-pillars was measured from the micrographs and

Table 3. Details of the parameters-combination used in the deburring experiments

Sample number	Deburring fluid	SOD (mm)	Power (%)
S1	DI water	2	100
S2	DI water + 3% Al ₂ O ₃	5	20
S3	DI water + 3% Al ₂ O ₃	5	60
S4	DI water + 3% Al ₂ O ₃	5	100
S5	DI water + 3% Al ₂ O ₃	2	100
S6	DI water + 3% Al ₂ O ₃	8	100

recorded after each ten-second deburring step. A typical top burr area measurement is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4. Typical top burr on a micro-pillar showing burr area measurement

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Pillar integrity and damage

The condition of the micro-pillars on Al 6061 and copper after deburring at all the parameters is given in table 4. Micro-pillars on Al 6061 were found broken on samples S4 and S5 after 20 s and 10 s of deburring, respectively. The rest of the samples of aluminium and all the micro-pillars on copper have not incurred any damage even after deburring for 30 s.

The micro-pillars on samples S4 and S5 on Al 6061 before and after deburring are shown in figure 5. Based on the deburring parameters used for these samples (see table 3), it can be inferred that the stand-off distance has a more profound effect on deburring than varying power has. At an SOD of 2 mm, all the micro-pillars were found broken after 10 s of deburring (sample S5), while at an SOD of 5 mm, one of the micro-pillars was intact after 20 s.

Figure 6 shows two samples on Al 6061 and copper with the micro-pillars neither broken nor bent. Other than those shown in figure 5, the rest of the samples have not

Table 4. Condition of the micro-pillars on Al 6061 and copper after deburring at different parameters

Sample number	Al 6061	Copper
S1	intact	intact
S2	intact	intact
S3	intact	intact
S4	broken after 20 s	intact
S5	broken after 10 s	intact
S6	intact	intact

Figure 5. Micro-pillars on Al 6061 showing pillar damage (a) sample S4 as-machined, (b) sample S4 after 20 s of deburring, (c) sample S5 as-machined, (d) sample S5 after 10 s of deburring

suffered any kind of damage to the pillar integrity. This is an interesting observation, particularly in copper, where none of the micro-pillars has suffered any form of damage after deburring. This can be attributed to the higher fracture toughness of copper than Al 6061 (see table 1).

The broken pillars seen in figure 5 have been examined closely. The base of the broken pillars on Al 6061 are shown in figure 7. Close-up views of the damaged region in figure 7 show excessive plastic deformation at the base of broken pillars. Along with heavy plastic deformation, a few pits are visible, shown encircled in figure 7b. These may have been caused by the impact of the abrasive particles, being the mechanism of

Figure 6. Micro-pillars on some samples with pillars intact and undamaged (a) sample S3 of Al 6061 as-machined, (b) sample S3 of Al 6061 after 30 s of deburring, (c) sample S2 of copper as-machined, (d) sample S2 of copper after 30 s of deburring

deburring, as established in an earlier study [23]. Further, the pillars may have failed by ductile failure mode and the damaged surface is suggestive of nucleation, growth and coalescence of voids, which are visible in figure 7 [28, 29].

Figure 7. (a) Base of the broken pillar of sample S5 of Al 6061 (SOD = 2 mm, power = 100%) after 10 s of deburring, (b) magnified view of the base in (a) showing the damaged region (pits are encircled)

3.2 Burr removal

In both the work materials, the bottom burrs were completely removed at all the deburring parameters after 30 s. This is mainly because the bottom burrs were attached to a very small area at one corner at the base of the micro-pillars. Bottom burr removal occurred within 10 s in most of the samples, posing a difficulty in their systematic study. Hence, top burr removal is quantitatively investigated in the present study.

The typical views of the condition of the micro-pillars before and after deburring are shown in figure 8 for Al 6061 (samples S1 and S3) and figure 9 for copper (samples S1 and S5). It is evident from the figures that the addition of abrasive particles has significantly improved the deburring performance over pure water cavitation in both Al 6061 and copper. Pure water cavitation has managed to reduce burrs to some extent, but could not remove the burrs completely.

Figure 8. Top view of the micro-pillars on Al 6061 showing top burrs, (a) sample S1 as-machined, (b) sample S1 after 30 s of deburring (pure water cavitation), (c) sample S3 as-machined, (d) sample S3 after 30 s of deburring (abrasive deburring)

The area of the top burrs was measured in all the samples after every 10 s of deburring by analysing the SEM images of the micro-pillars. The extent of deburring is measured in each case according to eq. 1.

Figure 9. Top view of the micro-pillars on copper showing top burrs, (a) sample S1 as-machined, (b) sample S1 after 30 s of deburring (pure water cavitation), (c) sample S5 as-machined, (d) sample S5 after 30 s of deburring (abrasive deburring)

$$\text{burr removal (\%)} = \frac{A_0 - A_t}{A_0} \times 100, \quad (1)$$

where A_0 is the area of top burrs on the as-machined micro-pillars and A_t is the area of top burrs on the micro-pillars after deburring for a time t .

The extent of burr removal in all the samples is plotted in figure 10. Volumetric burr removal could not be measured due to a very small amount of mass loss by deburring as compared to the bulk mass of the sample, hence the area of the burrs was measured in each case. At all the parameters, a significant amount of burr removal has occurred within the first ten seconds (86 – 90%). After 30 s, this has increased to around 93.4% for copper (sample S5) and 88.2% for aluminium (sample S3). In the case of pure water cavitation, around 51.5% and 53.1% burr reduction was observed after 10 s in Al 6061 and copper, respectively. This has increased to 68.1% and 67.4% after 30 s. This is mainly because of the deburring mechanism in the present study, which is burr removal by the impact of abrasive particles accelerated by ultrasonic cavitation. Pure water cavitation has also played a role in deburring, but abrasive impact is the more

significant phenomenon observed in the present study. In an earlier study, Kumar et al. [23] have established the mechanism deburring as mainly by the impact of the abrasive particles.

Figure 10. Percentage of burrs removed on micro-pillars at various parameters: (a) top burr vs time for Al 6061; (b) close-up view of (a); (c) top burr vs time for copper; (d) close-up view of (c)

Top burr reduction after 10 s for both Al 6061 and copper has been plotted as shown in figure 11. It can be seen that the abrasive deburring (at any parameter) is more effective in removing burrs as compared to pure water cavitation. Maximum deburring was observed to be 88.75% for Al 6061 (sample S4) and 90.1% for copper (sample S5), whereas in the case of pure water cavitation, deburring after 10 s was 51.5% for Al 6061 and 53.1% for copper. It can be seen that deburring is not very effective in the case of pure water cavitation (sample S1) in both the work materials, whereas the addition of abrasive particles has significantly increased the extent of deburring at all the parameters studied. This establishes the effectiveness of the deburring process by adding abrasive particles to the deburring fluid over pure water cavitation deburring. Further, by employing a probe sonotrode, deburring has been achieved in a significantly shorter time (10 s) as compared to studies in literature, which have reported a deburring time of 60 min to a few hours [20, 21, 30, 31]. The effectiveness of abrasive deburring over pure water cavitation has also been established in an earlier study [23]. This study further establishes that, upon the proper selection of process parameters, the

ultrasonic-assisted abrasive micro-deburring process is a suitable process for removing burrs from micromachined structures within a short processing time without causing significant damage to the components.

Figure 11. Top burr reduction after 10 s of processing on (a) Al 6061; (b) copper at various parameters

4 Conclusions

In the present study, an ultrasonic-assisted abrasive micro-deburring technique using a probe sonotrode has been employed for deburring of high-aspect-ratio micro-pillars machined on Al 6061 and oxygen-free high-conductivity copper. The following conclusions are drawn from the study:

- The mechanism of deburring is predominantly by the impact of abrasive particles accelerated by ultrasonic cavitation, and to a minor extent, by the cavitation effect itself, as seen from the extent of burr removal plots.
- Micro-pillars on Al 6061 were found damaged at lower stand-off distance values (2 mm and 5 mm) and undamaged at the rest of the parameters. It can be inferred that varying the stand-off distance has a more profound effect on deburring than varying power.
- Micro-pillars were intact and undamaged at all the parameters of deburring on copper, and for most parameters on Al 6061. This can be attributed to the higher fracture toughness of copper than that of Al 6061.
- Maximum top burr removal was achieved in a very short time, i.e., about 88.75% burr reduction for Al 6061 (sample S4) and 90.1% for copper (sample S5) after 10 s of deburring. This is significantly faster than the deburring processes described in earlier studies (60 min to a few hours using pure water cavitation).

- In the case of pure water cavitation, deburring extent was observed to be about 51.5% for Al 6061 and 53.1% for copper after 10 s and has increased to 68.1% and 67.4% after 30 s. This shows that pure water cavitation has a minor role to play in deburring, but is not as effective as the addition of abrasive particles.
- The use of abrasive particles and ultrasonic cavitation using a probe sonotrode has resulted in a significantly shorter processing time as compared to literature. Upon proper selection of deburring parameters, the process can achieve successful deburring of micromachined structures while minimising part damage.

CRedit author statement

A. Sravan Kumar: Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – Original draft.

Sankha Deb: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing – Review & editing.

S. Paul: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Resources, Supervision, Writing – Review & editing.

Conflict of interest

A. Sravan Kumar, Sankha Deb, S. Paul have patent titled "Ultrasonic vibration assisted abrasive micro-deburring employing a sonotrode" pending to Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur.

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